

MODERN APPROACHES TO COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF LOCALLY ADVANCED GASTRIC CANCER: A CLINICAL PERSPECTIVE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928452>

Introduction

Locally advanced gastric cancer (LAGC) is one of the most challenging malignancies in terms of treatment and patient outcomes. As a stage III cancer, LAGC is defined by tumor invasion into surrounding tissues and lymph nodes, but without distant metastasis. Gastric cancer remains the fifth most common cancer globally and is responsible for over 700,000 deaths each year, making it the third leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide (Bray et al., 2018). The aggressive nature of LAGC, coupled with its frequent diagnosis at an advanced stage, makes treatment particularly difficult. However, in recent years, significant advancements in surgical techniques, chemotherapy regimens, radiotherapy approaches, and the development of targeted and immunotherapies have transformed the treatment landscape for this disease.

The current management of LAGC is highly dependent on multimodal treatment strategies that involve a combination of surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy. The goal is to achieve complete tumor resection (R0 resection) and reduce the risk of recurrence, while minimizing treatment-related toxicities. Surgery alone, while effective for early-stage disease, is not sufficient for LAGC due to the high likelihood of micrometastatic disease and local invasion. This has led to the adoption of perioperative chemotherapy as a standard approach, aimed at improving surgical outcomes and overall survival. Furthermore, advancements in molecular biology have introduced novel targeted therapies that selectively attack cancer cells with specific genetic alterations, offering new hope for patients with limited treatment options.

The role of radiotherapy in LAGC has evolved over time, particularly with the advent of more precise radiotherapy techniques like intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT), which allows for better targeting of tumors while sparing healthy tissues. Immunotherapy, another breakthrough in the treatment of various cancers, has also entered the scene for gastric cancer. Immune checkpoint inhibitors, such as pembrolizumab, have shown promise in patients with specific biomarkers, particularly those with high microsatellite instability

(MSI) or programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) expression. These recent advancements reflect a shift towards more personalized treatment strategies based on the molecular characteristics of each patient's tumor.

Despite these advancements, the prognosis for patients with LAGC remains poor, with 5-year survival rates ranging from 20% to 40%, depending on the stage at diagnosis and the effectiveness of the chosen treatment strategy (Van Cutsem et al., 2016). As such, there is an ongoing need to refine treatment approaches, optimize perioperative strategies, and identify novel therapeutic targets. This review aims to explore the most current and promising approaches to the comprehensive treatment of LAGC, focusing on the integration of surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and targeted therapies. Additionally, the potential role of immunotherapy in treating LAGC will be examined, as well as future directions for improving patient outcomes through personalized medicine.

Surgical Approaches

Surgery remains the cornerstone of curative treatment for LAGC, with the primary goal being to achieve a complete (R0) resection, where no microscopic residual tumor remains. This often involves either a total or subtotal gastrectomy, depending on the location of the tumor. Radical gastrectomy with D2 lymphadenectomy is the standard surgical procedure recommended for LAGC, as it involves the removal of the stomach along with a wide dissection of the regional lymph nodes. Studies have shown that D2 lymphadenectomy improves overall survival and reduces recurrence rates compared to less extensive dissections, particularly in centers with expertise in gastric cancer surgery (Schmidt et al., 2020).

Minimally invasive surgical techniques, such as laparoscopic and robotic-assisted surgery, have gained popularity in recent years due to their potential to reduce perioperative morbidity and promote faster recovery without compromising oncological outcomes. While open surgery remains the standard for many institutions, particularly in cases of large or deeply invasive tumors, laparoscopic surgery has been shown to be a viable alternative for select patients with LAGC. A meta-analysis by Zhang et al. (2019) demonstrated that laparoscopic gastrectomy with D2 lymphadenectomy was associated with similar long-term survival rates to open surgery, but with lower rates of postoperative complications, such as wound infections and respiratory issues.

Robotic-assisted surgery, although less widely available, offers several advantages over conventional laparoscopy, including greater precision, improved dexterity, and enhanced visualization, which may be beneficial in

complex cases (Zhang et al., 2019). However, the long-term oncological outcomes of robotic surgery for LAGC are still under investigation, and more randomized controlled trials are needed to establish its role in routine clinical practice.

Perioperative Chemotherapy

The use of chemotherapy in LAGC has become a key component of treatment, particularly in the perioperative setting. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy, administered before surgery, aims to shrink the tumor and reduce micrometastases, making it easier to achieve an R0 resection. Additionally, preoperative chemotherapy has been shown to improve long-term survival by reducing the risk of recurrence. Several landmark trials have established the benefit of perioperative chemotherapy, including the MAGIC trial, which demonstrated that patients receiving chemotherapy before and after surgery had significantly improved overall survival compared to those undergoing surgery alone (Cunningham et al., 2006).

More recently, the FLOT (fluorouracil, leucovorin, oxaliplatin, and docetaxel) regimen has emerged as the preferred chemotherapy protocol for LAGC, based on the results of the FLOT4 trial. This trial showed that patients treated with perioperative FLOT had superior overall survival and disease-free survival compared to those treated with the older ECF/ECX (epirubicin, cisplatin, and fluorouracil/capecitabine) regimen (Al-Batran et al., 2019). The FLOT regimen has now become the standard of care for patients with resectable LAGC in many countries, offering a more effective option for controlling the disease both before and after surgery.

Radiotherapy

While the role of radiotherapy in the management of LAGC has been less well-defined than that of surgery and chemotherapy, it is increasingly recognized as an important component of multimodal therapy. Adjuvant chemoradiotherapy, delivered after surgery, can improve local control by targeting any remaining microscopic cancer cells in the tumor bed or lymph nodes. The INT-0116 trial was one of the first studies to demonstrate the benefit of adjuvant chemoradiotherapy, showing improved survival rates in patients with resected gastric cancer who received this combination compared to surgery alone (Macdonald et al., 2001).

Intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) has further enhanced the effectiveness of radiotherapy by allowing for more precise targeting of the tumor while minimizing radiation exposure to surrounding healthy tissues, such

as the liver and kidneys. This has reduced the risk of treatment-related toxicities, such as gastrointestinal complications, and has made radiotherapy a more attractive option for patients with LAGC who may not be candidates for more aggressive surgery (Kim et al., 2020).

Targeted Therapy

In recent years, the development of targeted therapies has revolutionized the treatment of many cancers, including gastric cancer. Targeted therapies are designed to attack specific molecules involved in cancer growth and progression, making them more selective and potentially less toxic than traditional chemotherapy. In gastric cancer, the most well-established target is the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2), which is overexpressed in approximately 20% of patients with LAGC (Bang et al., 2010).

Trastuzumab, an anti-HER2 monoclonal antibody, is the first targeted therapy to show a significant survival benefit when combined with chemotherapy in patients with HER2-positive advanced gastric cancer. The ToGA trial demonstrated that adding trastuzumab to chemotherapy improved median overall survival from 11.1 months to 13.8 months in this patient population (Bang et al., 2010). Since then, trastuzumab has become a standard treatment for HER2-positive gastric cancer, and ongoing research is exploring other potential targets, such as VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor) and MET (mesenchymal-epithelial transition factor).

Conclusion

The comprehensive treatment of locally advanced gastric cancer involves a multimodal approach that integrates surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and increasingly, targeted and immunotherapies. While significant progress has been made in improving survival rates, particularly with the introduction of perioperative chemotherapy and targeted therapies like trastuzumab, the prognosis for many patients remains poor. The recent advent of immunotherapy has opened new avenues for treatment, offering hope for a subset of patients with specific biomarkers. Future research will likely focus on refining personalized treatment strategies, optimizing combination therapies, and improving the quality of life for patients undergoing treatment. Through continued innovation and collaboration, it is hoped that the outcomes for patients with LAGC will continue to improve in the coming years.

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